

NFDI and PUNCH

NFDI

Nationale ForschungsDaten
Infrastruktur - National
Research Data Infrastructure

NFDI vision

Data as a common good
for excellent research,
organised by the scientific
community in Germany.

Consortia

represent a scientific
or thematic
community within the
NFDI.

PUNCH4NFDI

Particles, Universe,
NuClei and Hadrons
for NFDI

www.punch4nfdi.de

Fact sheet

- The non-profit association Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V., based in Karlsruhe, was founded in October 2020 to coordinate the activities involved in setting up the NFDI. <https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en>
- The consortia were selected in a science-led process managed by the German Research Foundation (DFG).
- Currently, 26 consortia are funded, covering Humanities, Social Sciences, Engineering Sciences, Life Sciences and Natural Sciences. <https://www.nfdi.de/consortia/?lang=en>
- Base4NFDI is a joint initiative of all 26 consortia with the goal to integrate and establish basic services as common, interoperable solutions. <https://base4nfdi.de/>

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